

Research

A qualitative study examining the resilience of rural migrated mothers' experiences of detachment from their children upon migrating to Jinhua City

Shikchhya Yonzon*¹, Prof. Dr. Zhangjun Wang², Misbah Shafait Abbasi³

¹Department of Comparative Education, Zhejiang Normal University, Jinhua 321000, China

²College of Teacher Education, Zhejiang Normal University, China

³Department of Comparative Education, Zhejiang Normal University, China

Abstract: In recent years, developing countries like the People's Republic of China have seen significant socio-economic and political growth (Ma, 2020). This economic revolution has led to tremendous progress for Chinese citizens, offering new opportunities and insights (Murphy, 2021). The growth primarily stems from the establishment of various manufacturing companies, factories, industries, and real estate developments in urban areas, which generate numerous job opportunities. To meet global demands, urban cities in China require substantial human resources, often drawing from a rural population (Ye Jingzhong, 2011). Many rural residents migrate to urban areas in search of better job prospects and living standards. This migration trend includes a substantial number of women, comprising one-third of all rural migrant workers (Yinni Peng, 2017). This paper specifically explores the resilience of migrant mothers in China, focusing on those who have left children behind in their rural homes. The study adopts a qualitative approach, utilizing semi-structured interviews and observations as primary research instruments. Ethical considerations were meticulously observed throughout the data collection process, adhering to both research norms and Chinese migration policies. The research highlights a gap in understanding the challenges faced by migrant mothers, particularly those who balance their roles as mothers with the demands of employment, often when their husbands travel for work, leaving children behind. The study conducted two rounds of qualitative interviews with 12 migrant mothers employed in Jinhua City. Given the limited existing research on the resilience of migrant mothers (Agadjanian, 2018), this research aims to underscore the importance of resilience in overcoming daily challenges. The qualitative study described in this paper aims to achieve two primary objectives: (i) Explore the perspectives and experiences of migrant mothers in China, and (ii) Propose interventions that could enhance resilience among migrant mothers. By shedding light on these women's stories, this research seeks to contribute to a better understanding of their experiences and inform policies and interventions that support their resilience amidst adversity.

Keywords: Resilience, Migration, Economy, Government, Rural workers,

*Corresponding Author: shikchhyayonzon@zjnu.edu.cn

Accepted: 31 July, 2024; **Published:** 07 August, 2024

How to cite this article: Shikchhya, Y., Zhangjun, W., & Misbah, A.S. (2024). A qualitative study examining the resilience of rural migrated mothers' experiences of detachment from their children upon migrating to Jinhua City. *North American Academic Research*, 7(8), 74-96. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13759312>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2023 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Introduction

The research is an analysis of the resilience of migrant mothers in China. The new economic revolution of the People's Republic of China has created new growth resulting economic boom. China opened the door to employment and economic prosperity which resulted in the establishment of various factories, industries, manufacturing companies and the development of real estate. China has become an industry to the world (Garnaut & Song, 2012a). China's economy has been increasing by nine to ten percent per year. China's GDP grew 5.2% in 2023 and China's economy is growing by 5% each year apart from 2020 and 2022, where two years was badly affected by COVID related lockdown. With the increasing number of these companies need larger workers with low wages. On the other hand, slower living standard in rural areas attracts lots of rural workers to come and work in urban cities because rural people can earn more money in a month than in a year in urban industrialized cities (Guo & Qiao, 2020). Out of the total migrant workers, one-third of workers are women, who decided to come to the city area and work as decided to come to city area and work as labour migrant workers. According to (Zhu, 2012). Since, the 1980s when the Chinese government opened economic reforms and opened its wings to international markets(Garnaut & Song, 2012b). China's urban and major city turns out to be the industrial and business hubs. The new economic revolution was dependent on low-wage manufacturing to produce excessive goods for international exports. Urban industries and manufacturing companies need a huge number of workers with low wages, these employment opportunities dragged lots of rural migrant mothers. Migrant Mother, on the other hand with left-behind children, shares different stories. The researcher in this paper tries to extract the risk and protective factors. These factors determine the resilience of migrant mothers challenging all the problems in their lives. The research paper tries to highlight the importance of relationships with their children, friends and family, their day-to-day lifestyle and other factors that lead towards resilience. The research also extracts the characteristics of resilient women and mothers. The researcher's main target is to find the components influencing migrant mothers and providing the zeal to work and sustain their lives. This paper focuses on the resilience and the factors affecting the resilience of migrant mothers despite all the challenges and obstacles they are facing as mothers, women and migrant workers.

Resilience

Resilience is all about being able to overcome unexpected situations and circumstances. It is the capacity to recover quickly from difficulties and toughness in life (Fleming & Ledogar, 2008) "Resilience is the process of adopting new situations in the face of various sources of stress such as tragedy, trauma and threats. It is the capacity to recover quickly from various obstacles which also means "bouncing back" from difficult experiences. Being resilient doesn't mean extraordinary, it's commonly demonstrated. In today's world, many people are not satisfied with their lives, often facing trauma, emotional pain, and sadness. Resilience is not a fixed trait that some people have while others do not. Instead, it encompasses behaviors, thoughts, and actions that can be learned and developed by anyone. Resilience refers to positive adaptation, or the ability to maintain or regain mental health, despite experiencing adversity(Herrman, 2011) (Wald et al., 2006) "Resilient People opt to be more flexible and comfortable. Flexible in the way that they can deal with the problems and flexible in the way they react emotionally to stress. They don't react to a particular style of coping mechanism, but they bounce back from one coping strategy to another according to particular situations and circumstances. When things get tough, some people continue to "swim along" while others "nearly sink" people who can swim through difficult times are more resilient. They bounce back from stressful experiences. (Wald et al., 2006-b)further explained the need for resiliency research has found that people who can bounce back live longer and have

better healthy and happy relationships. They are more successful in their education, personal life and career. They carry the characteristics of self-control and self-awareness. They can solve problems according to the favorable circumstances and environment. They are emotionally and mentally flexible to face fears. Resiliency helps people to view problems and challenges as opportunities and always learn from mistakes and overcome past mistakes, according to Resilience: Parent Information Handout. According to (AL Siebert, 2010) Resilience is really important in today's world. In today's competitive world, everyone feels pressured to be better and get more work done with high standards and quality with fewer people consuming less time and utilizing with limited budget. Resilience helps in coping with unexpected situations and circumstances and learning to cope and react to overcome unwanted adversities. It is the process of successfully adapting to any kinds of obstacles and challenges life experiences. Resilient people overcome adversity, bounce back from failure and stand after falling several times.

Internal Migration in China

Since, the late 1970s economic reforms have brought the major changes in the rural part of China. The migration from rural to urban migration in China represents one of the greatest internal migrations as the people from the rural area wants to migrant to urban for the better opportunity and meet the demand of laborer in urban areas (Zhou, 2020). The migration is a rural-urban migration economic revolution, people started to migrate to urban areas to become more economically sound and a quest for better living standards. According to (Xiachu Hun, 2012). In 2009, there were 145 million rural-urban migrations in China. 160 million people i.e. 12 percent of the total world population left remote areas to work in cities. The motivation was obvious. In 1978, everyone was poor in rural which was 40 per cent less than in urban areas. Communist China opened doors, and factories around coastal towns, and farmers could make more money in a month than in a year by growing rice. Migrant workers from the poor in lands such as Guizhou, Sichuan and Anhui moved to city areas for better economic and financial opportunities. In 1980, farmers lived less than one in a day. 10 million from 1990-1995 were migrated, 32 million migrated from 1995-2000 and yet another 38 million over the next 5 years by 2011, 160 million rural Chinese were working far from home. (2001-2010) migration contributed to nearly 20 percent of Chinese economic growth but it has all harmed at a personal cost. Many migrants spend years away from their families. Industrialization also caused terrible pollution but many felt a national and economic impact that made it worthwhile. In the 1990s the gap between rural and urban China was a serious problem. The city of Shenzhen had 12 million people in 2010 and it's set to keep on growing. The EIU forecast the population will hit 15 million by 2020. CEic, peen world tables; The Economist estimates. In the 30 years since 1979, China's urban population has rapidly grown to 622 million till 2009. Migrant people in China are generally members of a floating population, a migrant people who primarily migrate in urban China without local household registration status through the Chinese Hukou system. So, the rural migrant workers are mostly excluded from local educational resources and social welfare policies. Migrant workers are not necessarily people from rural migrated to urban but also people who live in urban with rural household registration, Kim Wan Chan. China's reform and Open" economic policy. It creates new growth resulting economic boom with rapid increases in China and Large foreign trade investments. Many factories and manufacturing industries in eastern urban areas. On the other hand, slower income growth and poor living standards in rural families excessively increased the demand for low-cost labour in China's new economic business i.e. manufacturing sector which pushed a large amount of rural migrant workers into urban areas. According to a recent report by the China National Bureau of Statistics, 44.4 per cent of new-generation migrant workers are employed in manufacturing companies compared to 31.5 per cent of previous generations.

Left behind children and migrate women in China

Left behind children in China refers to those children whose parents have gone to work from rural to urban areas. These children are generally raised by single parents or their grandparents. According to Center on China's Economy &

Institution, 2024, One in 5 children are grown up without one or both of their parents. (Katie Hunt, 2013) worries that China is creating a generation of loneliness as they see growing anxiety, poor grades and depression among left-behind children. (Wan William, 2013 stated that one in five children live in villages without their parents. According to All-China Women's Foundation, Modern Chinese society is experiencing great economic growth where on the other side millions of children are growing across China with parentless generations. The major reason for left-behind children is because of China's Hukou system where there is no provision for education, health and other social security to migrant children. (Yi Fai, 2015) states that approximately 61 million left-behind children are there in China which is 21.88 per cent of the total child population in China. These children are not only from economically underdeveloped provinces but are also from well-developed cities with sound economies and a scope of high job opportunities. The lives of women in China drastically changed after the rise of the People's Republic of China, which publicly announced its commitment towards gender equality and encouraged women's roles in the development of the nation. If we use female labour force participation as the indicator to measure gender equality. China would be one of the most egalitarian countries in the world. After the People's Republic China increased dramatically after the founding this almost reached the universal level. By the 1950s women's contribution to family income increased by 20 percent. The new economic revolution of the People's Republic of China's dependence on low-wage manufacturing to produce excessive goods for international migrants. Urban industries and factories need a huge number of workers. Lots of rural migrant women as urban girls first like to complete their education qualification. According to the Women's Foundation, the statistical ratio of male migrant workers outnumbers the female migrants 2:1 which means women consist of 20 percent of the total floating population. However, in some industrial areas such as Guangdong and Shenzhen, they prefer women to men. Especially, women who are younger and unmarried so that they can work for longer hours without any stress from family. Young women who haven't got access to education and better opportunities take advantage of paying lower wages and deprivation from benefits and other incentives. Thus, there has always been a gender disparity in terms of wages among men and women. This has consequently encouraged the labour market to unequal gender pay gaps.

Statement of Problem

After the economic revolution, China experienced one of the largest migrations in human history. The development of the country's main economy relies heavily on industrial growth, which in turn requires a substantial workforce. With the rapid pace of economic transformation, industries and factories have offered jobs to tens of millions of workers. Migrant workers, seeking better futures and opportunities, have flocked to these industries. Notably, over one-third of these migrant labourers are women. Generally, migrant women who seek jobs in urban and industrial areas come from rural regions and most of them are illiterate. The conditions for migrant labour mothers working in urban and major cities are very poor and vulnerable. Despite making significant sacrifices, rampant poverty and limited job opportunities in the countryside compel many to migrate for work. These workers often face the harsh reality of low wages and high living costs. According to National Bureau of Statistics of China (CNBS), 2024 The urbanization rate of permanent residents reached 66.16 percent, 0.94 percentage points higher than that at the end of 2022.

Migrant women face multiple pressures: professional demands, a patriarchal society, and social exclusion. As migrant workers, they experience disparities in social welfare; as workers, they are exploited by capital; and as women, they endure gender violence. This paper outlines the need for resilience among migrant women in China, focusing on migrant mothers. Although these women are capable of coping and sustaining themselves in challenging environments, they face numerous obstacles during their journey towards resilience. These migrant mothers are compelled to work under pressure, endure long hours, and live away from their hometowns, separated from their families, children, and loved ones. The research highlights the plight of these mothers, who must navigate completely new commercial cities without their children. Children, in turn, can act as a support system to help their mothers gain resilience, but those raised without their parents often exhibit isolation or violent behavior. Therefore, this paper highlights various

problems and key components hindering resilience among migrant mothers in China.

Findings and Discussions

1.1 Study Sample: Migration pattern & Women's social location

A centuries-long history of internal migration in China has led to the routine depletion of migrant women from many rural communities. Today, more than one-third of Chinese are migrating for work in urban and industrialized cities. Internal migration from rural to big cities such as Shanghai, Beijing, Guangzhou, Shenzhen and provinces with high capita income are the most common destinations. The economy of China is greatly dependent on internal labor migration. This major demographic shift has changed household composition throughout China. Migrant mothers with left-behind children also play a vital role in domestic migration. Participants were between 20 and 49 years old. Women from a variety of ethnic groups were interviewed about their working status. Factory workers, cooks, restaurant workers and others. None of the participants reported that they were educated. Approximately more than half of the women interviewed (before migration) lived in joint families, with the other women living separately from, although not necessarily far from, their in-laws. Nearly all women's spouses were currently migrated to other major commercial cities (n=12), while one woman's husband is working in his hometown looking after his children. All the migrant mothers have recently worked in Jinhua however before coming to Jinhua most of them had worked in a variety of locations, including Shenzhen, Beijing, Shanghai and Hangzhou. Migrant mothers would return (from time to time or every year), especially during spring festivals and summer holidays. Across interviews, participants discussed the effects of their lives upon migration. The following themes explored in the following sections relieve migrant mothers of both risk and protective factors. How these women are gaining resilience even after the adverse past and difficult situations.

Migration of women trajectories by their home towns according to participants. Home towns of migrant mothers include Guizhou, Hunan, Henan, Anhui, Jiangxi and Sichuan.

Background of Migrant Mothers

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with migrant mothers of left-behind children; these women are currently working in Jinhua, one of the major commercial cities of China. Twelve Chinese women were actively interviewed. The research was outlined by a combined Theoretical and Practical Framework and approaches. The research sample for the qualitative study was chosen by purposive sampling. Each respondent was recruited based on chosen purposive sampling. Currently, mothers of age (20-49) were recruited due to this study's focus on the resilience of migrant mothers. Eligible women were residents of various provinces of China such as Gui Zhou, Henan, Chong Qi, Hunan, Xian and Sichuan and had a labour migration experience, defined as having lived away from home for work for at least six months continuously. Women were recruited to ensure variation in migration experience (e.g. current destination, duration of absence, and migration history)

1.1 Age of Resilience Migrant mothers

The age plays a vital role in shaping the scope of migrant mothers. The age of the mother is also important for self-identity and self-esteem. So, this situation is very striking in all this regard. After, interviewing 12 respondents gave

some actual information about migrant mothers with left-behind children under different age groups. The interview transcript follows the age of migrant mothers ranging from 18 to 40 and above. The highest percentage of migrant mothers is found in the age of 30-39. The participation of middle age groups is higher compared to younger and older. In China, the average age of a mother is around 20 to 40. So, the highest age range interviewed is from 30-39 is the highest among all.

Age	Numbers
15-20	1
20-25	3
25-30	3
30-35	2
35-40	2
40-45	1
45 and above	0

1.2 Number of Children: Gaining Resilience

Children play a vital role in shaping the resilience of migrant mothers. While interviewing migrant mothers all the resilience migrant mothers focus on children, their upbringing and other educational issues. The more the children, the more the required expenditure and responsibility. By researching about their number of children. It will be easy to draw the outlined problems and the main motive towards resilience. The given below is a chart illustrates the number of children possessed by resilient migrant mothers in China.

Migrant Mothers	Children
Anonymous 1	1
Anonymous 2	2
Anonymous 3	2
Anonymous 4	2
Anonymous 5	3
Anonymous 6	1
Anonymous 7	2
Anonymous 8	2
Anonymous 9	1
Anonymous 10	3
Anonymous 11	1
Anonymous 12	2

1.3 Education Qualification

Education is one of the most integral parts. The education qualifications of migrant mothers also determine the level of work performed in their workplace. From the below-drawn table, a researcher wants to identify the basic background of resilient migrant mothers focusing on educational qualifications and experiences. While interviewing the migrant mothers' women, education and academic qualification also determine the level of resilience towards their lives.

Education Qualification	No. of Migrant Mothers
Primary	10

Secondary	2
Higher Secondary	-
University	-
Total	12

1.4 Resilience Migrant Mothers: Work Involved

Migrant mothers who were interviewed in the research are generally not educated or only studied till primary schooling. Most of the migrant mothers with left-behind children are working in low wages salary in small shops with minimum wages. Among the 12 migrated mothers working in Jinhua; almost all of them are working as a factory worker, restaurant workers, housekeepers and so on.

1.	Factory workers
2.	Restaurant workers
3.	Shopkeeper
4.	Housekeepers in Hotels
5.	Cook in Hotels, restaurants and in small shops

Discussion: Background of Migrant Mothers

Table 1.1 describes the age of migrant mothers interviewed. Lots of migrant mothers are between the age of 20-25 and 25-30 years of age. These women are at the tender age to perform their high-potential work performance. We find the amount of resilience is high in this age. As these migrated mothers have aspirations and desire to do well in their young and capable age. Table 1.2 illustrates the number of children possessed by migrant mothers. From, the research the maximum number of children is 3 and the least number of children is one. When interviewing the migrant mothers, the mothers who have a less number of children are happy and comfortable compared to those with the highest number of children possession. Migrant mothers with two or more two children have lots of problems, and a compulsion to work more and higher responsibilities. Table 1.3 describes that most of the resilient migrant mothers are educated as they are compelled to do household work due to extreme poverty. Out of 12 Migrant mothers interviewed 10 respondents attended primary schooling and 2 respondents attended secondary schooling. From, this table it is clear that the lots of migrant mothers working in Jinhua are not educated as they were deprived of education due to poverty, hardship and less access to school. Table 1.4 explains the resilience of migrant mother workers. All the migrant mothers interviewed were involved in the low-level level category of Jobs. Most of them are involved in Factory work, shopkeeping, house-keeping, cooking etc. These women also shared that they need to work for long periods and the amount they receive is very low. Hence, from the Background of Migrant mother’s analysis parts, we came to know that it is not easy to be resilient women during periods of hardship and lots of obstacles during their way.

Analyzing Resilience through Risk Factor: Practical Framework

The researcher used practical and theoretical frameworks to analyze the resilience of migrant mothers in China. Both internal and external protective factors were observed deeply to find out the results of resilience. The following points briefly describe the Risk factors that migrant mothers intervened to gain resilience in their day-to-day hardships and challenging lifestyle.

Reason behind working in the city

The limited employment opportunities in rural areas were a major concern and motivating factor leading migrant

mothers to migrate for work. While some women said the money that they earn in their hometown is way too low compared to what they earn in commercial cities. As E¹ said “See, I live in Hunan province. I used to work as a farmer but the money I used to receive was quite low to what I receive now in Jinhua working in a factory. I have a 14-year-old son and I am working far away from him just to fulfil his education and basic needs. My husband’s earnings are not enough to support our whole family including my parents’ in-laws. No one wants to leave their family and work in a new town but for migrant mothers like me. It’s our compulsion rather than the reason (E, late twenties, hometown in Hunan, and one son). Working in the urban commercial part of China earns more money than working in the rural part. The lack of good wages highlighted by M in rural areas is often linked with other economic reasons for migration. Migrant Mothers left their hometowns due to limited incomes and the need to earn money to support their families. The economic reasons given were intrinsically linked with the needs of the household, the family (including the extended family), and most importantly children’s education. Migrant mothers routinely mentioned children’s education and other expenses as the reason for working in another province of China.

P: “I have two sons. I want to give them all the happiness in the world. I want them to be very successful in their future unlike their parents

I: “Why do you migrant?”

P: “To earn money. If we were wealthy, I wouldn’t have to work outside like this. I am working here in Jinhua for the sake of the future of our children.” (XX, late twenties, hometown in Sichuan, two sons) Migration was often described as necessity and compulsion and was intimately linked with hopes for their children’s futures. As ZZ said, “We need to secure our future by working hard at the present.” (ZZ, mid-twenties, rural, one son and one daughter). Importantly, these quotations demonstrate the intertwined motivations for labour migrant mothers, which are the product of a lack of opportunities, low wages, economic demands on couples and families, responsibilities for the care and nurture of children back home, and desires for a better future. The economic stratification in rural and urban areas in China has led to internal migration from rural to urban areas, leaving children behind.

Age when they became mother to their first Child: Hindrance to social harmony

(YY, in their late twenties, in the hometown in Henan, one son, explains that she was just twenty years old when she first became a mother. She further explains, “I still don’t want to remember those days, I was working till the 7 months of my pregnancy. It was the hardest time of my life, I had to eat nutritious food but for me and my family, we were struggling to eat for a day. I wish and hope no women should be in those kinds of situations.”

P: Was your husband with you during your pregnancy period?

I: He was there with me on the day I conceived my elder son, but he had to leave for the job the same day.

I: What problem did you face after your delivery?

P: I wasn’t been able to work, in for minor things I need help from others. For two weeks, I was on complete bed rest, a doctor told me this was because of a lack of proteins and vitamins in my body.

P: What was the pushing factor for you in those difficult situations?

I: My parents-in-law took good care of me and my son. The most pushing factor was my newly born baby; he is the reason for our existence. His smiles brighten our whole home.

(LL, Home town in Henan, mother of two sons, rural) says I was just twenty-one years old when I first became a mother. I was so happy to feel motherhood because I always dreamt of being a mother since an early age, as I love children.

I: Was your fantasy world and your reality the me?

P: I was so wrong, being moa there carries a bigger responsibility on top of it being a mother also requires res mentally and physically fit and strong.

¹ Note: Pseudonyms were used to protect the confidentiality of participants.

I: what was the problem that you started noticing during your pregnancy time after you found out that after 6 months of my pry since, I started gaining weight and even after I work sometimes, I feel nauseous? I was so young physically and after my delivery, I started knowing the fact that raising a child needs a huge amount of time and money. Before, it was just two of us; my husband and me but after we became parents. It was my child as well; we needed to provide all the basic needs to him.

I: Do you regret it at the beginning of your motherhood period?

P: Despite all the hardship, I always enjoyed being a mother but what triggered me the most was that I couldn't provide all the love and materialist needs that my son needs.

I: What do you regret the most?

P: My son is now 11 years old. He calls me every time and asks me to buy this and that.

I: Can you fulfil all his demands?

P: That's why I feel so ashamed. He always complains that his classmate bought new things, and he has been using the same things for many years. Even if I wanted to buy them, I couldn't fulfill his need because we are poor.

S. No	Age when they became the mother	Number of respondents
1.	15-18	6
2.	18-21	3
3.	21-24	2
4.	24-28	1
5.	28 and above	0

From the above-mentioned conversation and table, it is clear that most of the migrant mothers became mothers at a tender age when they were not physically and mentally prepared. This is because they lack proper knowledge of family planning and other contraceptive device. However, they are still happy enjoying their womanhood and motherhood. They are ready to sacrifice their whole needs for the sake of their children's happiness, needs and demands.

Your First age when you left your children back home

Most of the migrant mother who migrated to Jinhua and was interviewed in this research explained the compulsion why they have to leave their small child and come to an urban city in search of job and career opportunities.

(L, Mid-thirties, one son, home town in Sichuan, rural) explained my son was just one year old when I came to Jinhua to search for work. I want my son to have a nutritious diet and healthy food but my husband's wages were not enough to take care of us as well as his parents. I cannot see my son and my family status like that so I came here so that my son can have a good and healthy diet. L Further explained I used to work for more than 12 hours just for the sake of my son's good future. I don't want my son to go through the same pain as we do."

(S, the early thirties, One son, one daughter, hometown in Sichuan, rural) explained I left my elder son when he was just 6 months old. I cannot even raise her properly which leads to having a very bad relationship with my son. He doesn't even feel comfortable to share things with me."

I: How do you feel when he behaves ignorantly?

P: I feel really sad but that was a compulsion, hope he will understand my sacrifices someday.

I: Do you blame yourself or your faith?

P: I am at least happy now; my son is studying in a good school. He is working hard and I am proud of him. I blame neither myself nor faith. I believe in hard work.

I: What do you want your son to be in future?

P: As a mother, I want him to be a good person apart from that he will choose his career according to his interests. I will not force him to become as such."

Most of the migrant mothers left their children at a very tender age. This leads to a detachment from their children. These migrant mothers' compulsion and poor economic conditions lead to migrants and work far from home.

The delay of partner communication about future children or family planning

Within the context of conversations focused on children and childrearing, some women described communicating with their husbands about family planning intentions. Such communication included using contraceptive methods whether women or their spouses wanted another child. This section explores how spousal migration was implicated in these conversations. More migrant mothers either did not discuss or delayed family planning-related conversations than women who said that they had talked about these matters with their migrating spouses. For most women, migration played a major, albeit complex, role in whether such discussion occurred. One migrant mother linked her decision to start using a hormonal form of contraception a week before her husband's return to conversations with him before his arrival. Other women described discussions she had with her husband before he left the last time about whether to keep her intrauterine device (IUD) or remove it; ultimately, they decided to keep it. In contrast, women –like PP below responded overtly that they did not discuss family planning with their non-resident husbands.

P: "We have two children so; we won't have another child."

I: "Do you think you will use a contraceptive method in future?"

P: "I don't know about that now we will decide when we meet. We don't talk on the phone about that." (PP, mid-twenties, hometown in Hunan, rural, two daughters)

The duration of current migration was a common reason for not discussing family planning.

"We have sufficient time; we have not thought about such things. It's only been ten months that I have been living far away from him." (CC, the late twenties, the home town in Sichuan, One daughter")

As CC communicated, the duration of long-distance relationship with her husband due to migration explained why such topics had not been broached. Most women said that they would discuss having another child, whether to use a contraceptive method or what method to use after the meeting.

"My son is just 5 years old. So, I think it is an appropriate time, however, I have to discuss with my husband about having the next child after we meet. I told him that I wanted another baby when but he did not agree that. (Y, one son, late twenties, home town in Hunan)

The duration of their distance was one of the reasons for not talking about family planning before spousal return.

Migrant mothers and their spousal busy schedules also functioned as barriers to having such conversations. When they were able to connect on the phone, they discussed their young child rather than any aspirations for future children.

I: "Do you talk to your husband about giving birth to another child."

P: "We used to talk about having another child, but not anymore."

I: "What did you use to talk about previously?"

P: "We used to discuss having another (child) once he comes back either a son or a daughter, but we do not talk about it anymore."

I: "Now will you talk about it before or after your meeting?"

P: "After we meet. I do my duty the whole day and sleep in my free time. So, there is hardly any time for us to talk. Whenever we get a chance to talk, it is about our daughter. I send him the photograph of my daughter, her videos which my parents send me from back home." (EE, Mid-twenties hometown in Sichuan, rural, one daughter)

For migrant mothers like EE and others, conversations usually revolved around the current child's well-being and the status of the household. Rather than discussing future children, women noted the limited time available for conversation and that contemporary issues, particularly those related to current children, were prioritized.

I: “Do you discuss with your husband about using family planning contraceptives?”

P: “No, we didn’t talk about it before either. Once he returns, we will have another child. When we talk on the phone, we talk about our daughter.” (JJ, mid-twenties, hometown in Hunan, rural, one daughter)

Ultimately, migrant mothers and their spousal migration play a vital role not only in whether spouses communicated about family planning but also when such communication occurred. For some duration of a husband’s absence meant that they felt no need to discuss future children or use of any contraceptive methods. For others, conversations focused on current household issues and children rather than aspirations or intentions for the future.

Relationship with Children Back Home

Relationship with children plays a vital role in shaping the resilience of migrant mothers. Left behind children back home shares a different relationship as compared with those mothers who have been living with their children. We interviewed 12 migrant mothers with different perspectives and asked them about their relationship with their children. These left-behinds lack the affection and proper care of their mothers.

CC, Late twenties, hometown in Sichuan, one daughter, “The most precious person in my life is my daughter. She has my heart. When I was with her for 2 years, she never left me and always followed me wherever I went. I still remember the day when I had to get Jinhua to come and she cried like anything. Two years after I migrated here, things were tough as she used to cry all the time but we couldn’t help each other. Now, she is more used to without me and is more comfortable with her grandparents than me. Sometimes, I feel so guilty that I cannot give time to her and now the relationship is not as good as it was before.”

YY, Mid-forties, two sons, one daughter, home town in Sichuan, “Now I am in my mid-forties, I couldn’t work as much as I used to work during my early and mid-twenties. My sons are young now and they can sense what is right and wrong. I am fortunate enough that my children understand my sacrifices. I heard most of the children complain that the parents are not taking good care or giving time but for me, my eldest son is very supportive and understanding. He is the guardian of our family as both I and his father have to leave home earlier to take care of their demands and day-to-day needs. He was the one to take care of his younger brother and sister and also make them realize we were far just for the sake of us. I travel back to my hometown once a year and we all unite one and they always count the day for me and my husband to come home.”

Resilience migrant mothers share that their relationship with their children depends on the age of their children. As per **CC, Late twenties, home town in Sichuan, and has one daughter** she is not happy with her relationship with her children as her daughter thinks she doesn’t make time for her. This proves resilience mothers like **CC** are facing relationship problems with their children. On, the other side of the story of **YY, in his forties, with two sons, one daughter, and a hometown in Sichuan** gave us a sigh of relief that with the level of understanding children will understand the sacrifices their parents made during their young age. **YY** believes that other migrants shouldn’t be worried about their relationship with children now, as per the time. They will understand their hardship and will also be thankful to all the migrant mothers for the scarifies they made for their bright future.

Work, working hours: Daily working schedule of migrant mothers.

All the migrant mothers interviewed work for more than 8 hours a day. Some even work for more than 12 hours based on their need for money. All migrant mothers as analyzed earlier are not educated and possess skilled knowledge. These mothers need to work for more hours as they are not skillful. The ultimate option for them is to work hard and work extra time to get more salary or wages.

Working Hours	Working Hour
6-8 Hours	1
8-10 hours	1

10-12 hours	3
12-14 hours	6
14-16 hours	1
16 and Above	1

From the above-mentioned table; the maximum number of migrant mothers are working more than 14 hours a day. When we asked them why they were working for long hours; **XX, Late twenties, with two sons, and home town in Sichuan** replied, "It is our compulsion to work for these many hours every day. I want my two growing sons to receive a good education and also give them all the necessary basic needs of children. I suffered a lot being poor but as a mother, I can't see them sharing the same faith. I live in Jinhua and I also need some savings for myself and pay bills for my rent, electricity and so on. City life is expensive and sustaining is hard if you do not earn more and work harder you need to work go back to your original place. No one will look after me, if I don't earn so I have to work for many hours and earn more. "

As per, "**JJ, mid-twenties, home town in Hunan, rural, and one daughter**) living in a city area is costly and on top of it carrying the responsibilities of children and grandparents is another reason to work hard. I am originally from Hunan province and I have my small daughter and grandparents back home.

I: How about your husband's salary

P: He earns very little. Last month, I became sick and couldn't go to work and with his wages it was so difficult. My daughter and my parents fully rely on us. I had to go to the hospital and things started getting tough when I spent much money on hospital and medicines. I have to work because, with the earnings of my husband, we can't fulfil the basic needs of a family.

I: Don't you get tired of working whole day and night?

P: Sometimes, I can't even sleep well because I have a backache problem. My job is tailoring so I have to sit and lean on a chair. The chair they provided is not convenient and comfortable. That is why I have back ache because I have seat on the same chair for more than 15 hours except at lunch and dinner time.

I: Why are you working for so long time?

P: I am working so that we all can live a comfortable life here in China. I don't want my daughter to sleep hungrily. My husband is very understanding and I don't want him to be pressured to earn more. My parents are old and sick and they need nutritious food and proper health check-up. My expenditure here in Jinhua. So, I have to work for more hours looking at all the treads and obstacles.

Discrimination faced by migrant mothers: Setting of working environments

Mothers who migrated from various places in China come to city areas to work and improve their socio-economic lives. The migrant mothers interviewed are from the rural part of China. These mothers share different family backgrounds which contrasts with the city area. In general, city life and rural areas is completely different from each other. This analysis part focuses on the discrimination and biases faced by migrant mothers. JJ, mid-twenties, home town in Hunan, rural, one daughter, "I am from Hunan province and lots of women working in Jinhua city are from Hunan. I never felt discriminated against in and out of my workstation because all of my colleagues and my friends are migrants. Almost all the time, I spend my spare time with my friends and even when I go outside, I travel whenever I feel any kind of discrimination in Jinhua. As, "XX, late twentieth, two sons and home town in Sichuan" shares a different experience in the migrated city. My workforce most of the staff is from Jinhua and they share a common language.

I: Do you feel isolated in the city?

P: Yes, I do because in my workforce almost all of my colleagues are from Jinhua. As I am only the migrated woman in my place

I: Why do you feel so?

P: They speak a common language and they have their mother tongue. I feel like they are talking about me as they can also speak Mandarin Chinese but they speak their native language. They also bias me in many things

I: What are the major things that you feel discrimination in Jinhua City?

P: Lots of things, I feel discriminated against when they plan something during their weekend and they never inform me about the plan. I also sometimes feel like I am a second-class citizen in the same country.

I: Do you want to settle down after your retirement or go back to your hometown?

P: I have a clear mind, once my children are self-dependent. I will go back to my home town and start doing agriculture.

I: Why don't you apply your plan now?

P: Because the money I will be earning by farming is very little. I have to take care of my children and family back home. After I retire my children will help financially and I don't need to worry about financial and economic needs.

I: What other discrimination do you feel outside your workplace?

P: I don't dress up well like other women do here in the city. I have to manage everything and I don't have time and extra money to focus on these things. This leads me to suffer a lot as they judge me based on my looks and my dress-up. They think I am economically very poor and treat me in other ways. Even when I am shopping, they don't entertain me well.

Discussion: Analyzing Resilience Migrant Mothers (Risk Factors)

This part describes and analyses the risk factors of migrant mothers and what are the hindrances to gaining resilience despite hardships and challenges in their lives. Table describes that most of the migrant mothers migrated from rural to Jinhua as there was an opportunity to work and earn more money with labour work compared to rural or in their hometown. The other reason is due to the experience of city lifestyle and maintaining their daily living standard as other city area people. Table, explaining that between 15 -and 18 years old lots of women married and were pregnant during this time. We all know that a woman plays a vital role in shaping their marriage and motherhood. From the above finding, we came to know that lots of women are illiterate and that is why lots of women lack knowledge about family structure, contraceptive devices and other means of family planning which results in early pregnancy. Topic on The communication with their partner as a spouse plays a vital role in any woman's life. Women are supposed to live outside without their families which leads to misunderstanding and communication barriers between each other. Topic on Relationship with children back home. Children play a vital role in enhancing the resilience of their mothers. During the interview session, almost all of them shared that the main reason for resilience is due to their children back home. Due, to the long-distance relationship and the Chinese law of the Hukou system these women shared a strange relationship with their children. Most of them are very disappointed with their faith as they cannot live with their children and see them growing with them. Children, on the other hand, are more attached to their grandparents and nearby surrounding people than to their parents who are working day and night for the sake of their family. Table that describes that women among 12 respondents more than half of the respondents are working more than 12 hours a day. When we asked them why they were working for a long time, they said it was because of their compulsion. The labour money is not high as compared to other high professional works since lots of women are uneducated, they are obliged to work for long periods to see and sustain themselves in the city as well as to look after their children's parents and in-laws back home. Topic that describes that migrant mothers face lots of discrimination while they are working in Jinhua City. Other workers and colleagues who are locally from Jinhua discriminate against migrant mothers. On the other hand, the migrant mother shares that they spend most of their time with their hometown friends so they don't feel any kind of hesitation or discrimination in the workplace.

Analyzing Resilience Migrant Mothers: Lens of Protective Factors

The below-mentioned data analysis part plays a crucial part in this research paper. This research paper tries to analyze the resilience of migrant mothers in China through various protective factors. These protective factors are the positive

aspects of gaining resilience despite their hard and complicated life. Each component mentioned below filters both internal and external protective factors among resilient migrant mothers. The research paper to grasp the main idea and their formula to gain resilience in their day-to-day lives.

Migrant mother’s husband’s jobs

In this research, the career development of husbands is mostly low-level jobs in China. The husband’s occupation determines their economic status and economic status determines their personality and career. Therefore, the development of migration in every factor is determined by the occupation of the husband. As, “(JJ, mid-twenties, home town in Hunan, rural, and one daughter)) explains My husband works in labour. He gets work based on the contract and the work is not permanent with a very low wage. With the income of my husband, we cannot survive with my two sons. So, I have to work to balance my family life well economically.

I: Till which standard did your husband study?

P: Both my husband and I belong to the lower class, and studying was never important to us as we were busy helping our parents in farming.

I: Does he regret not going to school?

P: I and my husband both regrets not going to school. That is why even in the economic crisis we support and encourage our two sons to study so that they will not bear any kinds of hardship in their lives like we are bearing.

The situation of most of the migrant mother and their husband is almost the same. As (Y, one son, He Nan, rural) explains My husband works for twelve hours a day but the pay he receives is very low and the money cannot even help our son get good food and support. If I don’t work the situation of our home will be critical so I have to leave my seven-year-old son and work day and night to support the economy of my family.

I: What does your husband do?

P: My husband sells flowers in Jinhua City.

I: Is his income alone can support your family?

P: No, his job is very seasonal and sometimes he doesn’t even earn a penny a day.

I: Why did he opt for that job?

P: My husband is not educated he has to opt for certain works which doesn’t require any skilled knowledge

Based on the interview taken with 12 migrant mothers, the following table can be drawn from the conversations.

S. No	Husband’s Job Category
1.	Logistic Labour
2.	Driver
3.	Cook in Restaurants
4.	Shop Keepers
5.	Labour Worker
6.	Restaurant Workers
7.	Factory Workers

From the abovementioned, it is clear that all the migrant mothers’ husbands indulge in small and labour work. As per the conversation, they said all the migrant mother’s husbands are not educated and lack skilled knowledge. This is why the economic condition of migrant women is very low and is also the reason why they should work because only with their husband’s earnings it is very difficult to sustain taking care of children, parents and parents-in-law back home.

Communication Technologies: Facilitating transnational conversations and implications for women’s daily lives

Cell phones were ubiquitous among the women interviewed. As one woman expressed “Even (my) mother-in-law has (a cell phone). Everyone carries one now.” (CC, late twenties, hometown in Hunan, Two sons and one daughter). Most

of these cell phones were connected to the Internet, which meant that women had multiple ways to contact their children, parents, parents-in-law and their husbands: by phone, WeChat or other mobile applications. We chat was most commonly identified by name, and if women had access to the internet, they would regularly send messages to their husbands and families back home. The availability of cell phones and Internet access marked, for several women, a change in how often they could talk with their children and families. Mary recounted a time early in her marriage when there were no mobile phone services in her village.

"I left my first child when he was just 1 years old. I came home after a year. There were no mobile phones for poor people like us, as it was too expensive. My family back home had to go to [a nearby village] to make a call. I used to call once every 6 months to 7 months." (CC, late twenties, hometown in Hunan, Two sons and one daughter)

Women highlighted how much more frequently they could talk with their families. Most women described talking with them daily, or even multiple times per day, although other women reported speaking once every couple a day or less than once a week. The frequency of conversation was affected by migrant women's availability. Multiple women emphasized that their schedule controlled when and whether they could connect, with restrictions on time limiting when they spoke.

I talk once every two or three days. I am very busy at work. I call them at night after dinner and ask about my children's education progress, their health condition" (YY, late twenties, home town in Henan, rural, one son)

Migrant mothers' availability, often at meal times or during breaks, affected other w family spent their time and determined the hen family's speaking. For example, June described how her conversation with her family back home fit into daily activities:

"...I wake up in the morning, drink tea, cook breakfast, and then I need to get ready to go to work. I go to the factory and spend the whole day till late evening or sometimes till night. Shortly after the lunch break happens. My children also get back from school. We have conversations over the lunch break, and after the break was over; I start doing my work. Then, after the work ends for the day. I take rest for some time, cook dinner, see my family pictures, sometimes call them if they are awake, and I sleep." (PP, mid-twenties, hometown in Hunan, rural, one son)

If they were unable to connect, PP's family would often repeatedly attempt to reach her.

"...I call them on the phone right away when we don't have conversations on WeChat. Now we talk through we chat mostly. If there is no Internet access, I call on the phone right away. They live in such a difficult place. So, I should keep calling them time and again. (PP, mid-twenties, home town in Hunan, rural, one son)

Other women shared similar stories calling repeatedly if they were unable to answer the phone.

When asked to describe their typical working days, most women highlighted how conversations with their families were important components of their days. Yet, for others, such conversations were much less consistent. In addition to their availability, external factors –including network errors, lack of money, children's timetable or poor Internet connection as discussed by PP above served to restrict when women talked with their families.

Conversations with absent spouses: Power dynamics and the prioritization of children's needs.

Women's conversations with their migrating husbands covered a range of topics focused on the household and family, including household responsibilities, children, health and wellness, mobility, finances, and the working environment. Although women most commonly mentioned talking about child-related topics, conversations about children were not distinct from discussions about other issues; children were routinely evoked in descriptions of conversations about household responsibilities, health and wellness, mobility (e.g. challenges to mobility due to childcare responsibilities), finances (e.g. children's education or daily needs), and work (e.g. prioritizing childcare overwork). Women did not frequently mention conversations about family planning with their spouses.

Women recounted conversations with their spouses by repeating the recommendations or advice that their husbands gave them. These conversations were frequently framed as "He tells me "Or "He says."

"We discuss raising children well, keeping them in line, their expenses and such. He tells me to focus on raising the children only, not earning lots of money and being rich" (CC, late twenties, hometown in Sichuan, One daughter", The priority placed on children during these conversations was clear. As this quotation from CC demonstrates, this advice was often focused on childcare and children's expenses. Women who engaged in work often mentioned that their husbands advised them to prioritize childcare over such work.

Some women spoke with their husbands about topics both big and small. As women recounted these conversations, they emphasized that such interactions consisted of their spouses telling them to do certain things like "eat and sleep on time," "visit family," or "see a doctor." The following quotation from TT is one such example:

"He tells me to go and visit family twice a year. He also tells me to eat properly and call his parents and children daily." (TT, the late thirties, a hometown in Gui Zhou, two sons and one daughter rural,)

Some women described "doing whatever he [the husband] says." S, whose husband was quite involved in her daily activities while he was away, said that her husband's consent was essential. She made sure to get his consent due to fear of abandonment if she were to challenge her role as a woman and wife by doing something on her own.

I: "What kinds of things do you decide on without your husband?"

P: Even though my husband is away. I don't make any decisions without the consent of my husband. For example; if I want to go and watch movies or take some lessons about something to develop my skills, I get consent from my husband. I do everything with the consent of my husband. I don't do anything on my own because being a woman and someone's wife if I do something without asking him and then, if he becomes angry." (S, the Early thirties, a hometown in Hunan, one son, rural)

In contrast, some women shared stories of ignoring or disregarding their husbands' instructions and making decisions without them, such as whether to visit family members or engage in work. For other women, as shown in the quotation below, everyday responsibilities and agriculture simply did not take priority in conversations with their spouses.

I: "Does your husband say anything about your work?"

P: "He doesn't say anything. He is not concerned about my work. He says do [it] if you can. [our] daughter is small so...I have to work to fulfil my daughter's desire and education."

I: "Do you discuss children's issues and other household work?"

P: "If there is something urgent then I ask him Otherwise I do it myself. (L, Mid-thirties Two sons. One daughter, hometown in Henan)

More urgent or important matters, particularly conversations about children and their needs took precedence during interactions on the phone or over the Internet. Discussions about everyday topics or daily life were, for some women, unnecessary to discuss with their husbands.

As one woman said, "Why would he ask about such a petty thing?" (ZZ, the Late thirties, two sons. One daughter, hometown in Henan)

RR also explained how she asked her husband only about crucial decisions and otherwise, she decided on her own.

"I say alone in Jinhua. So, everything I do is based on mutual discussion. If there is anything crucial, I ask my husband. I do the rest of the tasks myself." (YY, Mid-forties, two daughter's hometowns own in Hunan, rural)

Women also highlighted how their husband's migration restructured intimate relationships by reducing the support, both instrumental and emotional, that they received from their husbands while away YY further explains below the concrete ways in which her husband's absence affected the support she felt she had. Not only was it due to distance, but also because she did not share her emotions with him while he was away.

P: "I feel sad. Separation is different than being together."

I: "...What are the things you are worried about?"

P: "I am worried about my daughter. My husband is not with me neither is my daughter, what if she gets sick? I also worry about somebody saying badly to me. My husband is not with me to defend me."

I: What does your husband say about it?"

P: "What would he say? He says that he and I have the responsibility of earning for the family and looking after his family, so we can't stay together. He consoles me like that.

I: "What else does he say to console you?"

P: "He does not say much. Maybe because I don't complain a lot. I feel that it is no use sharing a lot of things with him since he is far from me." (YY, Mid-forties, two sons, one daughter, rural, home town in Sichuan)

As YY and other participants explained a spouse's migration affected the topics that took priority as women and their husbands navigated long-distance relationships. Transnational communication often focuses on children's needs and childrearing, rather than other intimate or household topics. Such communication facilitated men's involvement in some women's daily lives, while other women experienced greater autonomy in their husbands' absences.

Looking after the children back home

Children play a vital role in determining the resiliency of migrant mothers. All the migrant mothers interviewed leave their children back home. When we ask the questions that is looking after the children back home. (XX, mid-twenties, two sons, hometown in Henan) replies. "My parents-in-law are taking good care of my children. I visit my children once a year and my parents-in-law have provided them with all the love and support

I: "How is the relationship with your children back home?"

P: "Not as same as before."

I: Why?

P: I can see them once a year and they think I only fulfil their materialist things nothing more, there are no emotional attachments as such."

I: Can you share how the situation before when you were working as a homemaker was?

P: I still remember my son used to follow wherever I went, and the first time I left them they cried the whole night."

My Children always call me every day before they go to sleep. (YY, Sichuan, two daughters, rural)

I: "Do they call you regularly?"

P: It depends, sometimes I call them when I finish my work soon otherwise, they call me at the usual time every day."

I: Is there any change in relation after you migrated for your work?"

P: I make sure I visit my family twice or thrice a year, so this distance has also maintained our relationship as they value the importance of mother when I am not with them."

Visiting children also plays a vital role in determining their attachment to their children. Some women who left their children when they were young and visited quite a small number of times have disturbed relationships. On the other hand, those mothers who visit their children twice or thrice times have a healthy relationship with their children.

Discussion: Lens of Protective Factors

To remain resilient despite hardship and challenges is not an easy task. This Research tries to extract and find out the continuous protective factors that drive respondents (resilient migrant mothers) to remain resilient throughout the journey. The protective factors as per discussion and conversation say, that the husband plays a very vital role in defining protective factors. According to topic 4.4, Migrant mother's Husband's Jobs, despite all the economic hindrances. Husband's job assists migrant mothers economically, financially and emotionally. While interviewing migrant mothers they share that their husband has been the support system to them. They can share their hardships and their entire problem with their husbands without any fear. They have pressure to look after their family. Husband's Job and

economic support help the migrant workers to breathe peacefully. When interviewing, migrant mothers share that most of their husbands are involved in low-level job categories like logistic workers, drivers, cooks and labour workers. Topic 4.2 describes that communication technology plays a pivotal role. Having, long-distance relations with spouse, parents and their beloved children. Communication technology via various mediums plays significant roles. When asked

respondent, they shared that they talk with their dear once frequently via WeChat and other means of communication. These migrant women talk frequently with their children, parents and spouses (if they are far away). They also share that they have become more powerful and confident by working in the city and various commercial areas. They lastly share that we all women are resilient as we have come from adversity and tragic situations and still, we work hard to sustain ourselves in this world and be a better version of ourselves.

Theoretical Strength-Based Theory and Theory of Empowerment

Strength-based perspective emphasizes people's self-determination and strength. This theory is a way of viewing clients as resourceful and resilient in the face of difficulties and adversity. This theory is completely client-based and mainly focuses on future outcomes and strengths that people have while encountering various problems and crises. Through this perspective, all migrant women will change their way of seeing life and change attitudes which occur through self-transformation, the perspective towards work and colleagues, and also with the society and people they work with. This philosophy consists of the core existing values and belief that all individuals have their strengths and capacities. Through this theory, they try to focus on a person's ability, skills, interests and individual support system. Using a Strength-Based Perspective, data collected from responses is analyzed. This theory is a way of viewing clients as resilient and powerful even in difficult situations. Migrant mothers in this research paper who are resilient have been selected as respondents. Data analysis based on strength-based theory based on future outcomes. This theory focuses on the strength of the respondent during the hardship and how they overcome such tragic situations. In this paper; respondent was interviewed based on their strength mechanisms. The interviewer asked questions related to strength-based perspective and data was analyzed accordingly. Empowerment theory focuses on the issues of social inequalities, violation of rights and responsibilities and differences of some individuals, communities, and groups in a society. The theory of empowerment in social work is one of the most used theories that attempt to answer all the issues and various social actions of the individual lacking equal value and respect as other individuals. This theory focuses on human empowerment. Through Empowerment theory we can help a migrant mother to raise their voice against any kind of violation and voice for equality, gaining greater access to socially available resources to achieve personal and collective rewards. Through the theory of empowerment, we can help migrant mother enhance their skills and develop outer knowledge so that they can expand their wings and their influential power in their workplace and society as a whole. In this paper, the interviewer interviewed respondents based on a theory of empowerment. Through this theory, the responses were analyzed based on empowerment capacities and how we can suggest migrant mothers empower and strengthen themselves to gain resilience and achieve various goals and aspirations in life. Migrant mothers believe that as migrant workers. They became confident and self-dependent on themselves. Working in a city is not easy and living in a rural area. All the migrant mothers interviewed are from rural parts of China. In the 21st Century, situations are not as before. Technology and digitalization have changed the scenario of the country. China's improvement and use of technologies this year have made the country more technology-friendly. On the other hand, migrant mothers who came from rural areas have less idea about it. Along with time, migrant mothers adapt to the change and find themselves adapting to the city area. Migrant mothers believe that as migrant workers. They became confident and self-dependent on themselves. Working in a city is not easy and living in a rural area. All the migrant mothers interviewed are from rural parts of China. In the 21st Century, situations are not as before. Technology and digitalization have changed the scenario of the country. China's improvement and use of technologies this year have made the country more technology-friendly. On the other hand, migrant mothers who came from rural areas have less idea about it. Along with time, migrant mothers adapt to the change and find themselves adapting to the city area.

As, "XX, Late twenties, two sons, Home town in Sichuan, "When I first came to Jinhua, things were tough and I felt so bad about myself. I was so nervous and couldn't communicate with people much in town. I used to think I would never adopt the environment but time covers everything. With time, I kept updating myself and now I feel so proud. I feel confident within myself and also proud as my two sons are studying and getting a better education because of me. I

know life is hard, but still, I feel happy that I have moved on with life and not only transformed myself but updated the financial stability of my family. YY, in her late twenties, in a hometown in Henan, rural, one son) on the other hand also shares a similar story.

I: Can you share your first experience upon your arrival in Jinhua City?

P: I was shocked by the busy life here. Everyone is dressed up smartly. Technology has changed China; I felt it when I arrived in the city.

I: What were the changes you have seen in your hometown and the city?

P: Everyone is busy. Life is so fast and technology has changed everything. People are dressed up smartly and seems like everyone is rich.

I: What positive change did you feel after you came here?

P: At first, it was very difficult to manage almost everything but with time. I came to realize that I have come so far. I am so proud of myself wherever I stand now. I always see the initial life here and now the change I feel within myself. I believe migration taught me to be independent and confident in the earlier days of my life. I used to tell my friends to join me even when I went out in the market. Now, I am living alone in this big city and also taking care of my children and family and helping my husband financially. I feel so proud of myself.

Findings

The data were collected through interviews from the various migrant mothers who have left behind children, working in Jinhua city of Zhejiang, China. The basic fundamental goals of the research are to find out their risk factor and protective factors. With first-hand qualitative interviews, we can find out the actual problems, their day-to-day lifestyles and the status of their socioeconomic and day-to-day lifestyles. With the help of interviews, we got the following list of findings to know how they gain resilience after their tragic past.

- The main reason for resilience among migrant mothers is due to their children's future and further education.
- The age plays a vital role in shaping the scope of migrant mothers. The age of the mother is also important for self-identity and self-esteem. So, this situation is very striking in all this regard. The interview transcript gives some actual information about migrant mothers with left-behind children under different age groups. The highest percentage of migrant mothers is found in the age of 30-39. The participation of middle age groups is higher compared to younger and older. In China, the average age of a mother is around 20s to 40s. So, the age ranges from 30-39 is the highest among all.
- From the interview qualitative data, the migrant mothers are generally not from urban and city areas. They are generally from a rural part of China. The place found is usually near one from the city area. Though there are some places which are far away from city areas. The maximum migrant mothers are from Henan province as it is near Jinhua. Followed by the Sichuan and Hunan Province.
- The maximum migrant mothers are from Henan province as it is near Jinhua. Followed by the Sichuan and Hunan Province.
- Most of the migrant mothers are engaged in Factory work. Since the job doesn't need any qualification and the number of staff needed is more in number most of the migrant mothers are inclined towards factory work. The second indulgent work is cooking, very few migrant mothers own their work or shop and start working independently.
- Migration of people from one place to another in search of livelihood is our social reality along with the children which a family is unable to earn sufficient for survival. Then a child or whole family migrates for the sake of expectation of a better life or work migration of women from rural to urban areas has been increasing rapidly day by day in China.

- In this research, the career development of husbands is mostly low-level jobs in China. The husband's occupation determines their economic status and economic status determines their personality and career. Therefore, the development of migration in every factor is determined by the occupation of the husband.
- Husband is the support system to most of the migrant mothers as they help these migrant mothers in various emotional, financial and mental aspects.
- Generally, the Job of a migrant mother's husband is a low-level category of Job such as Driver, labourer, factory worker, logistic driver etc.
- The job of their husband is generally a low-paid job that doesn't require higher education and qualifications. From the first-hand interview, those husbands are also not working in their home town. In search of better jobs and facilities, most of them have migrated. The ratio of labour workers and drivers is higher than other jobs.
- The reason behind migrant mothers working is due to their husband's low income. This is why; migrant mothers have to be detached from their families especially their children and migrants in search of better jobs, to support the economic condition of their families.
- From the interview, it was found out that most of the migrant mothers work more than 10 hours per day and they have no holiday throughout the week. It's tragic to know the fact that most other mothers work more than 14 hours per day. Due to poverty and family pressure to earn more money to support the family financially and socially most of the migrant mothers work more than 14 hours. According to the National Labor Organization (ILO), the standard working time is 48 hours per week
- Most of the migrant women are busy with their lives. According to the interview, most of the migrant mothers visit their families in a year or at least once a year. They generally visit their family during spring festivals or during summer vacations. These migrant mothers miss their home but due to lack of financial difficulties, they have to stay away from their families and relatives.
- The entire migrant mother interviewed gave birth to their first child at a very tender age. This is because they lack knowledge about contraceptives and other family planning methods.
- Of all the mothers who migrated, everyone has been sacrificing their personal needs for the sake of their children's study and other basic needs and requirements.
- Lots of migrant mother's work in a workplace where they don't provide any social security. This leads to severe problems not only for migrant mothers but also for the nation as a whole. They work in a company where they don't have health insurance or any other social security. These women are working at high risk. Most workplaces don't provide social security because the companies are newly registered and have no social insurance except the daily wages and overtime wages.
- Lots of migrant mother's work day and night and also work overtime to support their families financially and economically. The work burden and load cause lots of serious health issues. The migrant mothers have problems with muscle and back aches. These problems occur because of excessive working hours continuously for a long time. The second most common problem is related to health as they feel nausea and weakness because migrant mothers lack a properly balanced diet and other basic diets.
- The left-behind children of migrant mothers are taken care of by their Parents-in-law. Since most of the migrant mother's husbands are also working in urban cities. The responsibilities to take care of children are generally parents or parents-in-law. From, the discussion most of the migrant mothers leave their children's responsibility to their parents and in-laws.
- The mothers who visit their children a couple of twice in a year have a healthy relationship in contrast to those mothers who visit once in a year or less than that.
- Of all the migrant mothers interviewed, every migrant mother is proud of China's economic and social

progress. They are proud how the country's technology and digitalization growth. However, they appeal that migrant workers should be provided with certain facilities and also a law on "left behind children" should be revised.

- Out of all the migrant mothers interviewed, migrant mothers share that all of them have disturbed relations with their children.
- The main reason for a disturbed relationship between the mother and child is due to long-distanced relations. A child only gets to see their mothers once or twice a year.
- Every other interviewed has planned something big and they want their children to be well-educated and lead an established life in the future.
- One-fourth of the total respondents claim that they have faced discrimination in their workforce whereas migrant mothers never faced any kind of discrimination in their workplace environment.
- All the migrant mothers are proud that they are surviving in a city and also earning so that they can take off their children and family.
- Of the migrant mothers, all of them felt a positive change within themselves after working for certain years in the city. They feel more confident, self-dependent and strong within themselves.
- One-third of the total migrant mothers said they want to go back to their hometown at the age of their retirement whereas remaining migrant mothers want to settle down in Jinhua with their children as they find Jinhua a convincing and comfortable city.
- Most of the migrant mothers share their feelings with their hometown friends whereas some migrant mothers share their feelings and emotions with their colleagues. One of the migrant mothers' shares that she doesn't like to share her things with anyone as she doesn't trust her friends and hence, shares her things with her family or only with her husband.

References

1. Berwick (2004) "Strength-based and male-focused and male approaches. "a. Baseline assessment Retrieved from Report.pdf
2. Ben Phelan (2014), "The story of a migrant mother
3. Bernard (1995) "Fostering Resilience in Children Council for Exceptional Children"
4. Boeije, Henie. (2002). A purposeful approach to the constant comparative method in the analysis of qualitative interviews. *Quality and Quantity*, 36 (4),391-409.
5. Boeijie, (2002). A purposeful approach to the constant comparative method in the analysis of qualitative interviews.
6. Chap again, B.k. (2015). Men's overseas migration and women's mobility and decision making in rural Nepalese families. Doctoral dissertation, Australian National University.
7. Clifford, David (2009). Spousal separation, selectivity and contextual effects.
8. Cohen, Jeffrey H. (2001). Transnational migration in rural: Dependency and the households 103 (4), 954-967.
9. Contraceptive practices and induced abortions status among internal migrant women,2015 Vol.15 (1)
10. Dayama, S.,Kosambiya,JK, & Kithara, SL.(2012).A qualitative approach to various factors affecting the health of seasonal Migrants.*Healthline, Journal of Indian Association of Preventive and Social Medicine*, 3(2), 27-31.
11. Denizen, N, & Lincoln, Y. (2000). *The handbook of qualitative research*.2nd ed. Thousand Oaks, Calif: Sage Publications.
12. Dorothy Bothell (August 2009) "Understanding 'Marginal' Perspectives: Towards a social theory of resilience.
13. Fleming, J., & Ledogar, R. J. (2008). *Resilience, an Evolving Concept: A Review of Literature Relevant to Aboriginal Research*.

14. Garnaut, R., & Song, L. (2012a). *China: New Engine of World Growth*.
15. Garnaut, R., & Song, L. (Eds.). (2012b). *China: Twenty years of economic reform*. ANU E Press.
16. Guo, Y., & Qiao, W. (2020). *Rural Migration and Urbanization in China: Historical Evolution and Coupling Pattern*.
17. Giri, Kalpana, & Darnhofer, Ika. (2010). Out migrating men: A window of opportunity for women's participation in community forestry? *Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research*.
18. Hamel, Jean -Yves. (2009). Information and communication technologies and migration.
19. Hannaford, Dinah. (2005). Technologies of the spouse: intimate surveillance.
20. Hannaford, Dinah. (2015). Technologies of the spouse: intimate surveillance in marriages. *Global Networks*, 15 (1),43-59.
21. HC, Health Communication Collaborative. (2014). Where we work.
22. Hirsch, Jennifer S. (2007). "Love makes a family". *Globalization, Marriage and the Modernizations of Gender Inequality*. Parker, R.G., EDS. (2007)
23. Herrman, H. (2011). *What Is Resilience?*
24. Hirsch, Jennifer. (2003). A courtship after marriage: Sexuality and love
25. IOM, International Organization for Migration. (2015). Health Vulnerabilities of Migrants from Nepal:
26. Isabelle Attanc (April 2014) "China being a woman in China today: A demography of gender"
27. Karoo Sullivan (August 10, 2012 "The role of women in China." Kirao Sullivan
28. Knowledge and attitude on maternal health care among rural-to-urban migrant women in Shanghai, China
29. Knowledge Wharton (December 2011) "How thin is the Glass Ceiling for China's businesswoman?"
30. Li Yifai(2015) "Left behind Child psychological condition white paper"
31. Liu Qiana (August 3, 2013) "China's left-behind Children lag"
32. Li, H., & Zahniser, S. (2002). The Determinants of Temporary Rural-to-Urban Migration in China. *Urban Studies*, 39(12), 2219-2235.
33. Ma, L. (2020). *Geography, trade, and internal migration in China*.
34. Michael Unger (March,2003)" Qualitative Contributions to Resilience
35. National Bureau of Statistics of China. Statistical Communiqué of the People's Republic of China on the 2017 National Economic and Social Development. Available online: http://www.stats.gov.cn/english/PressRelease/201802/t20180228_1585666.html (accessed on 19 July 2024).
36. Padilla, MB, Hirsch, JS (2007). Introduction: cross-cultural reflections on intimate intersections.
37. Pearson Jennifer (April 2006) "Reaching in. Reaching out"
38. Ping Zhou (March 2012) "China's Hukou System"
39. Rachel Murphy. (2021). *The Children of China's Great Migration*.
40. Socotra, Tomas. (2008). Overview Chapter 7: The rising importance of migrants for childbearing in Europe. *Demographic Research*, 19(9), 225-248.
41. Srivastha, Aashish & Thomson, S Bruce. (2009). Framework analysis: 4(2),72-79
42. Thieme,Susan,& Wyss, Simone.(2005).Migration patterns and remittance transfer in China
43. Tobin, Gerard A, & Begley, Cecily M. (2004). Methodological rigor within a qualitative framework, *Journal of advanced nursing*, 48 (4), 388-396.
44. Toyota, Mika, (2007). Bringing in the "Left Behind" back into the view in Asia: a critical framework for understanding the "migration -left behind"
45. Traue Marilee's & Uniqkaise Ari (October 9, 2010) "Understanding Youth Resilience in Papua New Guinea through Life Story."
46. Wald, J., Taylor, S., Asmundson, G. J. G., Jang, K. L., Stapleton, J., & McCreary, D. (2006.-a). *LITERATURE REVIEW OF CONCEPTS*.

47. Wald, J., Taylor, S., Asmundson, G. J. G., Jang, K. L., Stapleton, J., & McCreary, D. (2006.-b). *LITERATURE REVIEW OF CONCEPTS*.
48. Wilson, Ara. (2004). *The intimate economics of Bangkok: Tomboys, tycoons, and Avon ladies in the global city*: University of California Press.
49. Ye Jingzhong. (2011). *Left-behind children: The social price of China's economic boom*.
50. Zhao, Yaohui (July 1999). "Labor Migration and Earnings difference". The case of Rural China". *Economic development and cultural change*.

